

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15584681

Effect Of Health Education On Attitude And Practice Towards Occupational Hazard And Safety Measures Among Palm Oil Workers In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of health education on the attitudes, and practices toward occupational hazards and safety measures among of palm oil workers in Delta State, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design with 150 participants selected through multi-stage sampling was employed. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire (APOHSQ) with a reliability index of 0.96 for attitude and 0.89 for Practice. The questionnaire was administered before and after a structured health education intervention, achieving a 95.3% success rate. Data obtained was analyzed using SPSS v.25, involved percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test, and ANCOVA. Findings revealed significant post-intervention improvements in workers' KAP. Mean knowledge scores increased from 66.0% (pretest) to 85.1% (posttest), reflecting a gain of 19.1%. Attitudinal scores rose from an aggregate mean of 2.66 ± 1.15 to 3.46 ± 0.82 , with a mean gain of 0.80. Safety practices improved, the aggregate mean increased from 2.86 ± 1.04 to 3.17 ± 0.87 , reflecting a mean gain of 0.31. There was no significant difference in the effect of health education on knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures based on gender, age, and work experience ($P > 0.05$). Also, There was no significant difference in the effect of health education on attitude towards occupational hazards and safety measures based on gender, age, and work experience ($P > 0.05$). There was a significant difference in the effect of health education on knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures based on gender and work experience ($P < 0.05$), but not based on age ($P > 0.05$). The study concluded that health education significantly enhanced occupational health and safety outcomes such as knowledge, attitude and behaviour. It was recommended among others that government should institutionalize health education, strengthen safety regulations, and promote a culture of safety.

Keywords: Health Education, Knowledge, Occupational Hazards, Safety Measures, Palm Oil Workers

INTRODUCTION

Palm oil production is an agricultural venture that is both challenging and highly rewarding, endowed with significant technical and economic advantages as one of the most produced and consumed oils globally (Virgin et al., 2022). Gunn (2014) emphasized that palm oil appeals to users due to its year-round availability, affordability, and technical superiority among numerous edible oils. However, alongside its economic benefits, palm oil production exposes workers to multiple occupational hazards that can lead to serious health issues and accidents. Numerous injuries occur among oil palm workers, including

experienced ones familiar with equipment and work areas. Hazardous materials such as pesticides, fertilizers, flammable liquids, and solvents cause acute and chronic injuries and illnesses among workers. While mechanization has significantly increased production, it has also introduced new risks, including machine-related injuries (Decker, 2021).

In Delta State, Nigeria, where palm oil production is a major livelihood, many workers engage in traditional methods of cultivation, harvesting, and processing, often under hazardous and physically demanding conditions (Dennis & Romanus, 2018). Observations reveal that most workers display negative attitudes towards safety, often minimizing or ignoring the risks associated with their daily tasks. Unsafe beliefs, such as the idea that accidents are inevitable or that safety gear slows down work, are common. These beliefs directly influence poor practices like operating machinery without guards, climbing palm trees without harnesses, applying agrochemicals with bare hands, and carrying heavy loads without proper lifting techniques.

Moreover, practices such as working long hours without rest, improper storage of hazardous materials, and a general lack of reporting minor injuries all contribute to a culture of neglect and risk normalization. The absence of routine health surveillance, coupled with poor access to occupational health services, exacerbates the problem. The result is not only increased occupational injuries but also long-term health complications such as musculoskeletal disorders, respiratory diseases, dermatitis, and even chemical poisoning (ILO, 2018; Santoro et al., 2022).

The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2018) and Tarurhor and Emudainohwo (2020) emphasized the importance of preventive strategies, yet the reality on the ground often shows a wide gap between policy and practice. Among palm oil workers, protective equipment such as gloves, helmets, boots, and goggles is either unavailable, considered expensive, or rejected due to discomfort and heat, especially under Nigeria's tropical climate. Workers' personal risk perceptions, cultural beliefs, levels of education, and organizational factors such as employer commitment to safety profoundly shape attitudes and behaviors (Crawford et al., 2020).

Beyond individual and workplace-related factors, systemic issues like low levels of government regulation, poor labor inspection systems, and lack of enforcement of occupational health standards allow unsafe practices to flourish. Unlike industries where compliance is rigorously monitored, the agricultural sector in many developing countries, including Nigeria, often lacks structured occupational safety and health frameworks, leaving workers vulnerable to both immediate and cumulative health risks (WHO, 2020).

Health education interventions have proven effective in addressing such issues by increasing knowledge, shifting attitudes, and improving safety practices (Che Huei et al., 2020; Hasan & Kamardeen, 2022). Educational programs tailored to the literacy levels and local realities of palm oil workers are essential. Strategies such as using local languages, visual aids, practical demonstrations, and peer education have been found to improve understanding and retention of safety information (Achal, 2020). Workers trained through participatory methods such as role-playing, simulations, and peer-group discussions not only acquire technical knowledge but also develop a stronger sense of ownership and responsibility toward their own safety.

Importantly, a growing body of research highlights that changing safety behavior is not only about imparting knowledge but also about altering deep-seated attitudes and reinforcing positive norms. Theories like the Health Belief Model (Green et al., 2020) and Safety Culture Theory (Asamani, 2020) underline the importance of perceived susceptibility to harm, perceived benefits of preventive actions, self-efficacy, and cues to action in promoting safe work behavior. Strengthening workers' belief in their ability to protect themselves and showing the real benefits of safety practices such as fewer injuries, better earnings, and improved family life can motivate sustained change.

Delta State's economic reliance on palm oil makes it critical to safeguard the health and wellbeing of workers in this sector. Without effective health education and safety promotion, occupational hazards will continue to limit productivity, erode livelihoods, and undermine national agricultural policies aimed at food security and rural development (Reed & Mbenu, 2015; My Guide Nigeria, 2019).

Despite the severity of these occupational risks, few studies have focused specifically on the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of palm oil workers toward occupational hazards and safety measures in Delta State. Comparative studies from countries like Malaysia and Indonesia show that proactive health education programs drastically reduce work-related accidents and improve productivity in the palm oil sector (Naeni, 2015; Kushairi et al., 2019). Learning from these international best practices and adapting them to the Nigerian context could offer promising results.

Therefore, this study investigated the effect of health education interventions on the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding occupational hazards and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State, Nigeria by answering the following questions:

1. What is the effect of health education on attitude and practice towards occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State?
2. What is the effect of health education on attitude and practice towards occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil processing worker in Delta State based on selected demographic variables (gender, age and work experience)?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Health education has no significant effect on attitude and practice towards occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State.
2. Health education has no significant effect on attitude and practice towards occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil processing worker in Delta State based on selected demographic variables (gender, age and work experience).

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a pretest-posttest quasi-experimental research design. The study's population consisted of 1,522 local oil millers in Delta State, representing the total number of millers across the 25 Local Government Areas (Delta State Oil Millers Association [DSOMA], 2024). A sample of 150 participants was selected through multi-stage sampling. Data collection was carried out using a validated, structured questionnaire titled: Attitude, and Practice towards Occupational Hazard and Safety Questionnaire (APOHSQ)," with a reliability index of 0.96 for attitude and 0.89 for Practice. The instrument was divided into two sections: Section A contained 3 items aimed at gathering demographic information about the respondents, while Section B included items designed to assess the respondents' attitude and practice regarding occupational hazards and safety. The attitude subsection had 10 items, structured using a 4-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree [SA], Agree [A], Disagree [D], and Strongly Disagree [SD]), scored as 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. The practice subsection also included 10 items, structured with a 4-point Likert scale focusing on frequency (Always [A], Occasionally [O], Rarely [R], Never [N]), and scored as 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

The questionnaire was administered before a structured health education intervention. The intervention, which lasted six weeks, was designed to improve the workers' knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures. Following the intervention, the questionnaire was re-administered, achieving a 95.3% response rate. The data collected were analyzed using SPSS v.25, employing descriptive statistics (percentage, mean, standard deviation), t-tests, and ANCOVA.

RESULTS

Demographic Data

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Factor	Groups	F	%
Gender	Female	87	60.8
	Male	56	39.2
	Total	143	100.0
Age	≤20 years	9	6.3
	21-30 years	49	34.3
	31-40 years	43	30.1
	≥41 years	42	29.4
	Total	143	100.0
Work Experience	<1 year	8	5.6
	1-5 years	22	15.4
	6-10 years	31	21.7
	≥11 years	82	57.3
	Total	143	100.0

Table 1 above revealed that 87 study participants (60.8%) were females while 39.2% were males. This implied that more females engaged in palm oil processing business than males. The age distribution of the palm oil workers showed that majority of the participants (34.3%) are between 21–30 years, followed by those aged 31–40 years (30.1%) and ≥41 years (29.4%). Only 6.3% are 20 years or younger, indicating that most workers are adults in their productive age range. Also, the data revealed that majority of the participant, 57.3%, have over 11 years of experience. Those with 6–10 years of experience make up 21.7%, followed by 15.4% with 1–5 years, and only 5.6% have less than one year. This suggests a workforce with large industry experience.

Table 2: Mean analysis of the effect of health education on attitude towards occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta state

Items	Pretest (N =143)		Posttest (N =143)	
	\bar{x}	St.d	\bar{x}	St.d
37 Occupational health and safety rules are not meant only for those working in a company. (P)	2.77	1.06	3.59	0.73
38 Proper lifting techniques prevent back injuries when handling heavy palm oil products. (P)	2.64	1.11	3.38	0.89
39 Consuming food or drinks in the processing area is safe and does not pose any contamination risks. (N)	2.62	0.95	3.65	0.70
40 It is crucial to know the location of emergency exits and fire extinguishers in the palm oil mill. (P)	2.70	1.09	3.43	0.88
41 Safety training is only necessary for new employees and does not need to be refreshed regularly. (N)	2.66	1.18	3.12	1.00
42 It is unsafe to consume alcohol while working at the mill. (P)	2.52	1.22	3.23	1.00
43 It is ideal for workers to wear personal protective equipment while working at the mill. (P)	2.64	1.20	3.71	0.65
44 Ignoring small hazards such as poorly placed sharp objects is not good. (P)	2.62	1.28	3.57	0.73
45 It is not the sole duty of the government to provide PPE for local oil mill workers. (P)	2.66	1.05	3.43	0.85
46 Engaging in regular cleaning of the mill is generally good for the safety and health of workers. (P)	2.55	1.26	3.75	0.67
47 It is safe to operate machinery without following the lockout/tagout procedures in the palm oil mill. (N)	2.63	1.10	3.52	0.77
48 Regularly cleaning and maintaining equipment significantly reduces the risk of accidents in the palm oil mill. (P)	2.68	1.20	3.38	0.89
49 Workers do not need to wear masks when exposed to dust and fumes in the palm oil production area. (N)	2.67	1.12	3.65	0.70
50 Oil mill managers can enforce safety rules. (P)	2.54	1.24	3.43	0.88
51 I think safety first for myself and for others working at the mill. (P)	2.64	1.12	3.12	1.00
52 Wearing PPE does not reduce how much a worker can make in a day. (P)	2.74	1.11	3.30	0.99
53 Regular inspection of palm tree climbing ropes is essential in reducing the risk of fall accidents among harvesters. (P)	2.84	1.18	3.47	0.83
54 Proper placement of sharp objects after use significantly reduces incidents of cuts and puncture accidents. (P)	2.67	1.16	3.50	0.70
55 Wearing safety gadgets does not prevent accidents in the palm oil workplace. (N)	2.78	1.14	3.48	0.76
Aggregate	2.66	1.15	3.46	0.82
Aggregate Mean Gain			0.80	

Table 2 revealed that the mean analysis shows a positive shift in palm oil workers' attitudes toward occupational hazards and safety measures after the intervention. The aggregate mean score increased from 2.66 ± 1.15 in the pretest to 3.46 ± 0.82 in the posttest, with a mean gain of 0.80. This improvement indicates that the health education intervention effectively promoted positive attitudes among workers in Delta State.

Table 3: Mean analysis to establish the effect of health education on practices towards occupational safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State

Items	Pretest (N =143)		Posttest (N =143)	
	\bar{x}	St.d	\bar{x}	St.d
56	2.72	0.93	3.29	0.54
57	2.83	0.93	3.32	0.54
58	3.03	1.05	3.32	0.84
59	2.80	1.08	3.13	0.93
60	3.02	0.93	3.30	0.69
61	2.96	0.98	3.36	0.67
62	3.00	0.94	3.36	0.62
63	2.80	1.10	3.07	1.00
64	2.85	1.06	3.22	0.86
65	2.64	1.13	2.96	1.02
66	2.90	1.06	3.20	0.88
67	2.62	1.07	2.92	0.97
68	2.78	1.10	3.07	0.98
69	2.80	1.08	3.08	1.00
70	3.02	0.93	3.22	0.86
Aggregate	2.86	1.04	3.17	0.87
Aggregate Mean Gain	0.31			

The mean analysis indicates an improvement in the occupational safety practices of palm oil workers following the health education intervention. The aggregate mean score increased from 2.86 ± 1.04 in the pretest to 3.17 ± 0.87 in the posttest, with an aggregate mean gain of 0.31. This suggests that the health education intervention positively impacted the workers' adherence to safety practices.

Table 4: Summary of paired sample z-test analysis establishing the effect of health education on attitude towards occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State.

Variables	N	\bar{x}	St.D	Mean Diff	z-Stats	Eta ²	P.value
Pretest Aggregate Attitude	143	2.64	0.945				
Posttest Aggregate Attitude	143	3.49	0.638	0.846	8.923	0.359	0.000

P<0.05

Table 4 shows the paired t-test results indicate a significant improvement in the aggregate attitude towards occupational health and safety measures after the intervention. The pretest mean (2.64 ± 0.945) increased to a posttest mean of (3.49 ± 0.638), with a mean difference of 0.846. The results are statistically significant ($t = 8.923$, $p < 0.001$) with a partial eta squared value of 0.359, indicating a moderate effect size and substantial impact of the health education program. Hence, the intervention improve the attitudes of workers by 35.9%. Therefore, health education is an effective means of improving health and safety behaviour.

Table 5: Summary of paired sample z-test analysis establishing the effect of health education on practices towards safety measure among palm oil workers in Delta State.

Variables	N	\bar{x}	St.D	Mean Diff	z-Stats	Eta ²	P.value
Pretest Aggregate Practice	143	2.90	0.754				
Posttest Aggregate Practice	143	3.21	0.592	0.308	6.893	0.251	0.000

P<0.05

Table 5 indicates a significant improvement in occupational hazard control and safety practices among palm oil workers after health education. The pretest mean practice score ($\bar{x} = 2.90 \pm 0.754$) increased to the posttest mean score ($\bar{x} = 3.21 \pm 0.592$), with a mean difference of 0.308 and a z-statistic of 6.893 ($p < 0.001$). The partial eta squared (0.251) reveals that 25.1% of the improvement in safety practices is attributed to the health education intervention, demonstrating its substantial effect.

Table 6: Summary of ANCOVA analysis establishing the effect of health education on attitude towards occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil processing worker in Delta State based on selected demographic variables (gender, age and work experience).

Source	Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	11.453 ^a	22	.521	1.350	.155	.198
Intercept	568.464	1	568.464	1473.922	.000	.925
Gender	1.548E-5	1	1.548E-5	.000	.995	.000
Age	.360	3	.120	.311	.817	.008
Work_experience	.519	3	.173	.448	.719	.011
Gender * Age	2.560	3	.853	2.213	.090	.052
Gender *	3.349	3	1.116	2.894	.038	.067
Work_experience						
Age * Work_experience	1.443	6	.241	.624	.711	.030
Gender * Age *	.747	3	.249	.646	.587	.016
Work_experience						
Error	46.282	120	.386			
Total	1799.000	143				
Corrected Total	57.734	142				

The ANCOVA results in the table 6 indicate that demographic variables had varying effects on the posttest aggregate attitudes of palm oil workers toward occupational health and safety measures. Gender alone ($F = 0.000$, $p = 0.995$, $Eta^2 = 0.000$) and Age ($F = 0.311$, $p = 0.817$, $Eta^2 = 0.008$) were not significant predictors, suggesting that these variables did not independently influence the attitudes. Similarly, Work Experience ($F = 0.448$, $p = 0.719$, $Eta^2 = 0.011$) had no significant main effect. More so, the interactive effective of gender, age, work experience ($F = 0.646$, $p = 0.587$, $Eta^2 = 0.016$) were not significant, suggesting limited influence of these interactions on attitude outcomes. The results indicate that gender, age, work experience, and their interactions did not significantly influence posttest attitudes toward occupational health and safety measures among palm oil processing workers.

Table 7: Summary of ANCOVA analysis establishing the effect of Health education on practices towards occupational safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State based on selected demographic variables (gender, age and work experience).

Source	Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P.value	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	31.528 ^a	23	1.371	8.973	.022	.134
Intercept	20.243	1	20.243	32.515	.024	.127
Prepractice	16.281	1	16.281	106.575	.000	.472
Gender	.021	1	.021	5.135	.049	.110
Age	.801	3	.267	1.747	.161	.042
Work experience	.248	3	.083	6.541	.045	.130
Gender * Age	.242	3	.081	.528	.664	.013
Gender * Work_experience	.376	3	.125	.821	.485	.020
Age * Work_experience	.846	6	.141	.923	.481	.044
Gender * Age * Work_experience	.006	3	.002	.014	.998	.000
Error	18.179	119	.153			
Total	1523.000	143				
Corrected Total	49.706	142				

The ANCOVA results reveal that Gender ($F = 5.135$, $p=0.049$, $Eta^2 = 0.110$) and Work Experience ($F = 6.541$, $p=0.045$, $Eta^2 = 0.130$) significantly influenced occupational hazard control and safety practices among palm oil processing workers, indicating notable differences based on these variables. However, Age ($F= 1.747$, $p= 0.161$, $Eta^2 = 0.042$) did not show a significant effect. The interactive effect of Gender, Age, and Work Experience ($F = 0.014$, $p = 0.998$, $Eta^2 = 0.000$) was not significant, suggesting limited combined influence on safety practices. This highlights the individual significance of Gender and Work Experience but minimal combined demographic interaction. The results show that gender and work experience significantly influenced safety practices, while age and their combined interactions had minimal impact, emphasizing the importance of specific demographic factors.

DISCUSSION

The current study found that health education significantly improved workers' attitudes and safety practices toward occupational hazard control in palm oil processing in Delta State, Nigeria. Pre-intervention assessments showed moderately positive attitudes, which improved substantially after the intervention, with consistent gains across gender, age, and work experience. Workers better appreciated the importance of safety training and PPE. These findings align with studies by Kelechi and Adeoye (2020) and Taufik et al. (2019), which also reported positive shifts in worker attitudes following safety education. However, contrasting findings by Okoli and Asiegbu (2021) and Ma and Chan (2020) highlighted challenges, especially among older workers and the short-term nature of some interventions. In terms of safety practices, post-intervention data showed improved PPE use, better hygiene practices, and more diligent hazard reporting. These outcomes align with studies by Adeola and Oyebola (2021) and Chikezie et al. (2020), though Okonkwo et al. (2020) and Ahmed and Saeed (2019) noted that age and lack of ongoing reinforcement can limit lasting improvements. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for sustained, context-specific health education to ensure long-term safety behavior change.

The study revealed that health education significantly improved workers' attitudes toward occupational hazards and safety measures across all demographics. Younger workers (≤ 30 years) and females showed

slightly higher posttest gains, suggesting greater openness to learning. This aligns with Nwachukwu and Eze (2020), who reported greater attitudinal shifts among younger agricultural workers, and Adebayo and Salawu (2018), who found stronger safety attitudes among female industrial workers. However, Okafor and Obinna (2021) observed no gender differences post-training, attributing changes to organizational culture. Similarly, Olatunji and Yusuf (2019) noted that with experience-tailored programs, older workers could also achieve substantial attitude improvements. Overall, the current study supports the role of age and gender in shaping safety attitudes while acknowledging the influence of workplace dynamics.

On occupational hazard control and safety practices, the study showed significant improvements among palm oil workers across all demographics. Females exhibited marginally higher posttest scores in hazard elimination and PPE use, while workers with moderate experience (6–10 years) recorded the greatest gains. These findings agree with Adebayo and Yusuf (2019), who found better post-intervention practices among moderately experienced oil and gas workers, and Okonkwo and Akinola (2020), who observed stronger safety commitments among female manufacturing workers. Conversely, Olatunji and Adesina (2018) found no gender-based practice differences, and Nwachukwu and Eze (2020) reported that highly experienced construction workers outperformed others. The current study thus reinforces the importance of targeting gender and experience dynamics in designing effective health education programs.

CONCLUSION

The study underscores the transformative impact of health education interventions in significantly enhancing attitudes, and practices toward occupational safety among palm oil processing workers. The improvements observed in workers' adoption of safety-conscious attitudes, and adherence to safe practices demonstrate the power of targeted educational programs to create safer and healthier work environments.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In alignment with the findings of the study including its conclusions, the following were recommended:

1. Nigerian, most especially Delta State policymakers and agricultural business activities industry regulators should implement workplace safety policies that mandate periodic refresher training on the benefits of safety compliance. Employers should establish reward systems to recognize and incentivize workers who exhibit exemplary safety behavior. This approach would reinforce positive attitudes toward safety, fostering a workplace culture that values proactive risk management and compliance with established protocols.
2. Palm oil process company Employers should ensure the provision of adequate and accessible personal protective equipment (PPE) for all workers. This can be achieved by allocating sufficient resources for purchasing and maintaining PPE supplies and ensuring they are tailored to workers' specific roles. Industry regulators should enforce compliance through regular safety audits and inspections. This would empower workers to practice safety effectively and reduce the risk of workplace injuries and illnesses.

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